

Condensation Products of Some Substituted Aromatic Amino Compounds with Dehydro Acetic Acid

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In earlier communications¹, it was reported that dehydroacetic acid (I) exists in solution as an enol (II), the carbonyl group of which at C₃ condenses with amino group of primary amines, amino acids and other related compounds to give products (III).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(ArN = Ph N etc.)

In the present communication, some more condensation products of *o*-, *p*-anisidines; *o*-, *m*- and *p*-amino phenols; *p*-amino acetanilide; *p*-amino salicylic acid; *o*-amino benzoic acid; sulphapyridine; sulphathiazol; sulpha guanidine and sulpha diazine with dehydroacetic acid have been described.

Dehydroacetic acid was prepared by Arndt's method², with slight modification. The condensation of ethyl acetoacetate was carried out under atmospheric pressure and room temperature. The resultant alcohol was removed by distillation using a long fractionating column. The dark brown semisolid thus obtained was thoroughly cooled and kept over night. The crude product was treated with ice cold sodium hydroxide solution (1*N*) and filtered. The filtrate was treated gradually with dilute hydrochloric acid to precipitate dehydroacetic acid which was separated, washed, dried and recrystallized from alcohol (M.P. 108°, Yield 65%).

The residue left after the treatment of the crude product with ice cold sodium hydroxide solution is under investigation.

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1. Gupta and Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 421 and 874.
2. "Org. Syn." Coll., Vol. III, p. 231.

The condensations of substituted aromatic amino compounds with dehydroacetic acid were carried out in the same way as described earlier³. Equimolar ethanolic solutions of substituted aromatic amino compounds and dehydroacetic acid were refluxed over water bath for 5 hrs. On cooling the reaction mixture, the corresponding solid products were obtained which were separated and crystallized from alcohol.

The characteristics of the condensation products are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Condensation Products of Some Substituted Aromatic Amino Compounds with Dehydroacetic Acid

Sl. No.	Amino compounds used	Formula of the product	Colour	M.P. °C	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					F	R	F	R
1.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	Grey	109	—	—	4.80	5.14
2.	<i>o</i> -Amino phenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	Light-yellow	142	—	—	5.25	5.40
3.	<i>m</i> -Amino phenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	Dark-yellow	168	—	—	5.10	5.40
4.	<i>p</i> -Amino phenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	Yellow	164	—	—	5.15	5.40
5.	<i>p</i> -Amino acetanilide	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N	Brown	210	—	—	8.10	9.33
6.	<i>p</i> -Amino salicylic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₆ N	Red	230	—	—	4.25	4.62
7.	Anthranalic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₅ N	Black	167d	—	—	4.50	4.87
8.	Sulpha thiazol	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ S ₂	Brown	172	15.72	15.80	—	—
9.	Sulpha pyridine	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₃ S	Brown	182	7.98	8.02	—	—
10.	Sulpha guanidine	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄ S	Grey	190	8.58	8.79	—	—
11.	Sulpha diazine	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄ S	Brown	178	8.00	8.24	—	—

Yield of the Product 30 to 45%

F = Found, R = Required, d = Decomposed

The compounds 8–11 required 7 to 8 hrs for affording condensation products with dehydroacetic acid.

All the above condensation products give a positive test with ferric chloride indicating the presence of a free $\geq$ C–OH group. Moreover, these compounds do not react with characteristic ketonic reagents and, therefore, indicate that the ketonic group present in dehydroacetic acid at C₃ must have reacted with the amino group of the compounds under reference.

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